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CYTOTOXIC POTENTIAL OF ANDROGRAPHOLIDE AGAINST HUMAN LUNG ADENOCARCINOMA CELL LINES - A 549

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ABSTRACT

The present communication offers a new insight to the cytotoxic potential of Andrographolide against Human Lung Adenocarcinoma Epithelial Cell Lines, A-549 and its insensitivity against normal cell lines, L-132, employing MTT colorimetric assay. On the basis of viability, proliferation and activation of cells, andrographolide was found to be 77.52 % toxic for A-549 cell lines at 100µg/ml concentration whereas it did not show any remarkable toxicity against L-132 cell lines. Thus, Andrographolide may prove to be an anti-proliferative agent against tuberculosis associated lung cancer.

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INTRODUCTION

Globally, lung cancer is one of the major causes of cancer death that claims more than 1.3 million lives per year [18]. Instances of deaths are increasing with the growing uptake of tobacco use in the third world. Lung cancer expedites the growth of abnormal cells in the lung tissue causing lumps in one or both the lungs [2].

A-549 cell lines are Adenocarcinoma Human Alveolar Basal Epithelial Cells. The A-549 cell lines were first developed by Giard *et. al.* (1972) through the culture of excised cancerous lung tissue in an explanted tumor of a 58 year old Caucasian male. They were able to synthesize lecithin with high levels of de-saturated fatty acids, which are important to maintain membrane phospholipids in cell. A-549 Cell lines are now widely used as an *in vitro* model for Type II Pulmonary Epithelial Cells for drug metabolism and transfection [9].

L-132 cell lines are normal embryonic lung cells, used for primary isolation of entero-virus and also found to be sensitive to hepatitis virus. Though, some rationally viable methods, such as radiotherapy and chemotherapy, are available for treatment of cancer, these techniques have their own risks.

Thousands of herbal and traditional compounds are being screened world-wide to confirm their use as anti-cancerous drugs [6]. One such plant, *Andrographis paniculata* has been used in conventional *Siddha* and *Ayurveda* systems of medicine since medieval times [1]. The therapeutic value of *Andrographis paniculata* is due to its mechanism of action *via* enzyme induction. Apart from its general use as an immune-stimulant, the plant extract exhibits anti-typhoid, anti-fungal, anti-hepatotoxic, anti-biotic, anti-malarial, anti-hepatitic, anti-thrombogenic, anti-inflammatory, anti-pyretic and anti-snake venom properties [14].

Andrographolide, the prime constituent of the extract, is a bicyclic-diterphenoid lactone. Recent studies by Shrivastava & Garg (2013, 2014) have suggested its inhibitory effect on *Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex*. The present study is another effort to attest the cytotoxic potential of andrographolide in the treatment of Lung Cancer.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant extract

The leaves of *A. paniculata* were procured from nursery, dried in shade, & subsequently in hot air oven, for 30 minutes at low temperature and then pulverized into dust or powder form. The dried powder was then used for extraction with solvent ethanol [12].

Chemical analysis of Andrographolide

Thin layer chromatography (TLC) analysis was carried out for the detection of Andrographolide. A precoated plate of silica gel 60F254 (Merck) and mobile phase (chloroform : methanol : ethyl acetate - 8.0 : 1.5 : 1.0) were used. The ethanolic extracts fractionated by TLC were detected through UV radiation (Electronic UV Trans-illuminator :Rf of andrographolide = 0.58) [17].

Preparation of plant extracts (Standard concentration)

One mg of ethanol extract of Andrographolide was taken and dissolved in 10 ml sterile distilled water. Thus 100 µg/ml of stock was obtained as a standard concentration of Andrographolide. Ethanol extract were sterilized using 0.22 µm membrane filter and pasteurized at temperature 62° C for 15 minutes [3].

Preparation of stock solutions of antibiotics drugs

Different concentrations of antibiotics were prepared using water as a solvent. One mg of isoniazid and fluoroquinolones were taken and dissolved in 10 ml of sterile distilled water. Accordingly 100 µg/ml stocks of isoniazid and fluoroquinolone antibiotics were prepared. The Stocks were sterilized using 0.22 µm membrane filters. Different working concentrations (100, 33.33, 11.11, 3.77 and 1.23 µg/ml) were prepared using log₂ dilution [3].

Culture and Propagation of A-549 and L-132 cell lines:

Commercially available A-549 & L-132 cell lines were procured from Blossom Pharma & Biotech Research Center, Bhopal and were maintained in RPMI-1640 medium supplemented with 10% new born calf serum (NCS), L-glutamine (4mM), sodium pyruvate (1mM) and 2-mercaptoethanol (50µl). Cells were cultured in 6 well plates in the absence of antibiotics at all times.

Inoculation of different concentration of Andrographolide:

Different concentrations of Andrographolide (100-1.23µg/ml) were used for the screening of cytotoxic activity. These concentrations were inoculated in culture of A-549 & L-132 cell lines. The experiment was carried out with one separate control (No Andrographolide was added in both cell lines culture) [7] [8].

MTT Colorimetric assay:

Cells were plated in 96 well microtitre plate at densities ranging from 5 x 10⁵ cells per well and each cell density was tested in five wells. MTT (Sigma Aldrich) was dissolved in 5mg/ml in PBS (Mosmann, 1983). 20µl of MTT solution were added to each well and the microtitre plates were incubated at 37°C for 4 hours. Supernatants were then discarded and 200µl of acidified isopropanol (0.04 N HCl in isopropanol) was added to the cultures. The contents were mixed thoroughly using a multichannel pipette to dissolve the dark blue crystals of formazan. Plates were incubated at 37°C for 1 hour [5]. Absorbance values were determined at 570 nm by colorimeter. Data were expressed as mean absorbance value (OD) ± standard deviation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Each experiment was done five times and the mean values of percentage cytotoxicity and absorbance were presented (Table - 1). The relationship of cell density to absorbance is shown in Figure - 1. It was apparent that absorbance of L-132 normal lungs cell line was greater than A-549 lung carcinoma cell lines at the same concentration of Andrographolide. The Andrographolide depicted maximum cytotoxic action (77.52 %) at 100 µg/ml concentration against A-549 cell lines. Conversely, no significant effect was observed on the viability of L-132 cell lines at the same concentration of Andrographolide.

Figure 1: Percentage Cytotoxicity of Andrographolide against A-549 & L-132 Cell lines.

Method validation

Table 1: Absorbance and % Cytotoxicity of Andrographolide against A-549 & L-132 Cell lines.

Concentration µg/ml		Absorbance at 570nm	% Cytotoxicity
100	A-549 cell lines	0.231 ± 0.012	77.52 ± 0.34
	L-132 cell lines	0.712 ± 0.014	30.73 ± 0.50
33.33	A-549 cell lines	0.341 ± 0.003	66.82 ± 0.09
	L-132 cell lines	0.731 ± 0.014	28.89 ± 0.38
11.11	A-549 cell lines	0.371 ± 0.100	63.91 ± 0.63
	L-132 cell lines	0.890 ± 0.121	13.42 ± 0.67
3.77	A-549 cell lines	0.547 ± 0.070	46.78 ± 0.43
	L-132 cell lines	0.929 ± 0.140	09.63 ± 0.70
1.23	A-549 cell lines	0.710 ± 0.103	30.93 ± 0.61
	L-132 cell lines	1.023 ± 0.147	00.48 ± 0.99

Value are mean of absorbance and % cytotoxicity with ± SD (n =5)

DISCUSSION

Cancer is becoming one of the major public health burdens on both developed and developing countries. Several synthetic agents are used to reverse, suppress or prevent the disease but have their own side effects. Researches are going on to investigate the plant derived chemotherapeutic or herbal agents. Some medicinal plants have been studied *in vivo* & *in vitro* experimental models of cancer and have shown significant inhibition of cancer cell proliferation. Bachrach *et. al.* (2012) reported anticancer properties of *Withania somnifera*, *Crocus sativus* and *Vitexagnus cactus*. Kim *et. al.* (2000) isolated seven triterpenes from the stem bark of *Physocarpus intermedius* Schn. (Rosaceae). Of these, 3-O-caffeoyl-oleanolic acid, betulinic acid and the methyl ester of euscaphic acid were the most effective *in vitro* against A 549 cell lines.

International Association for the Study of Cancer (IASC, 2012) provides compelling evidences regarding increased lung cancer risk among people with tuberculosis. The incidence of lung cancer in tuberculosis patients was 11 times greater than people without tuberculosis. Garg & Shrivastava (2013 b, c) conducted *in-vitro* anti-mycobacterial activity of Andrographolide against *M. microti*, *M. bovis* and *M. canettii*. They calculated 96.38 ± 0.39% (*M. microti*), 98.0 ± 0.42 % (*M. bovis*) and 97.0 ± 0.82 % (*M. canettii*) of inhibition at 100 µg/ml.

Thus, Andrographolide may prove to be an anti-proliferative agent against tuberculosis associated lung cancer.

Authors' Statements

Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmad, M. and Asmawi, M. Z., Some pharmacological effects of aqueous extract of *Andrographis paniculata* Nees. International Conference on The Use of Traditional Medicine and Other Natural Products in Health-care (Abstracts). University Sains Malaysia, Malaysia, 1993, 122.
2. Alberg, A. J., Samet and J. M., Epidemiology of Lung Cancer. *Chest*. 2003, 123: 21-49.
3. Almola, Z., The inhibitory effect of *Henna lawsoniainermis* leaves of some fungi. *Iraq Academic Scientific Journal*. 2010, 10(5): 501-510.
4. Bachrach, Z., Contribution of Selected Medicinal Plants for Cancer Prevention and Therapy, *Acta Facultatis Medicae Naissensis*. 2012, 29 (3): 117-123.
5. Campling, B. G., Galbraith, P. R., and Cole, S. P. C., Use of the MTT assay for rapid determination of chemosensitivity of human leukemic blast cells. *Leukemia Res*. 1988, 12: 823.
6. Garg H. K. and Shrivastava, A., Application of nanotechnology and biocomputation for treatment of cancer, *The Pharma Innovation*. 2013 a, 2(6): 63-66.
7. Garg, H. K. and Shrivastava, A., Andrographolide induced succinate dehydrogenase activity in isolated mitochondrial fraction from different organ of Balb/c mice, *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences*. 2013 b, 6(4): 43-45.
8. Garg, H. K. and Shrivastava, A., Clinical use of Andrographolide as a potential drug against vole tuberculosis, *J. Pure Appl. Zool*. 2013 c, 1 (3): 223-226.
9. Giard, D. J., Aaronson, S. A., Todaro, G. J. Arnstein, P., Kersey, J. H., Dosik, H. and Parks W. P., "In vitro cultivation of human tumors: Establishment of cell lines derived from a series of solid tumors". *Journal of the National Cancer Institute*. 1973, 51 (5): 1417-23.
10. Kim, Y. K. and Yoon, S. K., Cytotoxic triterpenes from stem bark of *Physocarpus intermedius*. *Planta Med*. 2011, 68: 392-398.
11. Ibrahim, T., Esther, A. and Wang, Y., Anti-TB activity of *Seticulia setigera* Del., *The Pharma Innovation*. 2012, 1(3): 17-23.
12. Misra C. S., Pratyush K., Sagadevan L. D. M., James J., Veetil A. K. T. and Thankamani V., A comparative study on phytochemical screening and antibacterial activity of roots of *Alstonia scholaris* with the roots, leaves and stem bark. 2011, 58: 124-131.
13. Mosmann, T., Rapid colorimetric assay for cellular growth and survival: Application to proliferation and cytotoxicity assays. *J. Immunol. Methods*. 1983, 65: 55.
14. Najib, N. A., Rahman, N., Furuta, T., Kojima, S., Takane, K. and Ali, M. M., Anti-malarial activity of extracts of Malaysian medicinal plants. *J. Ethnopharmacol*. 1999, 64 : 249-254.
15. Shrivastava, A. and Garg, H. K., Cytotoxic potential of Andrographolide against bovine tuberculosis, *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences*. 2013 a, 8(5): 01-04.
16. Shrivastava, A. and Garg, H. K., Effect of Andrographolide on Proliferation of *Mycobacterium canetti*, *International Journal for Pharmaceutical Research Scholars*. 2014 b, 1(3): 410-413.
17. Sule A., Ahmed Q. U., Samah O. A. and Omar M. N., Screening for antibacterial activity of *Andrographis paniculata* used in Malaysian Folkloric Medicine: A possible alternative for the treatment of skin infections, *Ehtnobotanical Leaflets*. 2010, 14 : 445-56.
18. Youlden, D. R., The International Epidemiology of Lung Cancer: Geographical Distribution and Secular Trends. *Journal of Thoracic Oncology*. 2008, 3: 819-31.

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